

Phenyl-2-phenyl-4-thiazolyl Diketones

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Benzoyl ketoximes previously reported were hydrolysed to diketones. The diketones were characterised by their quinoxaline derivatives.

Preparation of 2-phenyl-4-thiazolylbenzoyl ketoximes is described in the previous paper¹. These benzoylketoximes were hydrolysed to diketones by following the method of Erlenmeyer and Ueberwasser². Isolated diketones were characterised by preparing their quinoxaline derivatives. The structures of these diketones were studied by I.R. spectra.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydrolysis of 2-Phenyl-4-thiazolylbenzoyl Ketoximes to Diketones.—The method of Erlenmeyer and Ueberwasser² was modified in the following manner:

Crude hydrobromide of 2-phenyl-4-thiazolylbenzoyl ketoxime (5 g.) was heated with sodium bisulphite (10 g) and glacial acetic acid (30 ml.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. on water bath. Heating was continued for 1 hr. more by adding sodium bisulphite (5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (20 ml.). The hot solution was then treated with conc. HCl (40 ml.) portionwise and heated on water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The mixture was allowed to cool and diluted with water. The gummy solid which precipitated was extracted with ether. Ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed through the ether solution till saturation. Ethereal solution containing diketone was removed from the precipitated gummy mass by decantation. Ether was removed and the remaining solid washed with water. The diketones obtained were crystallised from alcohol.

Quinoxaline Derivatives.—Alcohol solution containing the diketone and *o*-phenylenediamine in equimolecular proportion was warmed on water bath, when quinoxaline derivatives precipitated. These quinoxaline derivatives were crystallised from alcohol.

Structures of Diketones.—Structures of these diketones were studied by I. R. spectra by comparing them with benzil. Benzoylketoximes showed the prominent peak at 3.05μ assigned to -OH group from oxime. The diketones showed the absence of the above peak and a peak was observed at 6.0μ assigned to diketones. Benzil had the similar peak. Quinoxaline derivative had none of these peaks.

1. Bhagwat and Nargund, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 323.

2. Erlenmeyer and Ueberwasser, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1940, **23**, 197.

TABLE I

No	R	R ₁	R ₂	Formula	Properties	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
1.	H	H	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 90-91°C	N: 4.7	4.78
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 169-70°C	N: 11.4
2.	CH ₃	H	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow flakes, m.p. 93-94°C	4.51	4.56
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	Pale yellow micro needles, m.p. 105-106°C	10.94
3.	Cl	H	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ClNO ₂ S	Yellow green needles, m.p. 126-27°C	Cl: 10.72	10.84
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ S	Colourless silky needles, m.p. 154-55°C	Cl: 8.8
4.	OCH ₃	H	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NO ₃ S	Pale yellow flat needles, m.p. 116-17°C	N: 4.13	4.33
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	Colourless micro needles, m.p. 127-28°C	N: 10.51
5.	Cl	Cl(3)	H	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	Yellow micro needles, m.p. 132-33°C	Cl: 19.51	19.62
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	Pale brown micro needles, m.p. 153-54°C	Cl: 16.22
6.	Cl	Cl(2)	H	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	Yellow granules, m.p. 93-94°C	Cl: 19.55	19.62
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	Pale brown micro needles, m.p. 168-69°C	Cl: 16.2
7.	H	H	CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 103-104°C	N: 4.48	4.56
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 174-75°C	N: 10.92
8.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow crystals, m.p. 104-105°	N: 4.28	4.36
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ S	Pale yellow micro needles, m.p. 124-25°C	N: 10.6
9.	Cl	H	CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ClNO ₂ S	Yellow needles, m.p. 112-13°C	Cl: 10.31	10.40
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S	Yellow long needles, m.p. 172-73°C	Cl: 8.53
10.	OCH ₃	H	CH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO ₃ S	Pale yellow micro needles, m.p. 112-13°C	N: 4.05	4.15
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	Pale brown needles, m.p. 124-125°C	N: 10.18
11.	Cl	Cl(3)	CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow micro needles, m.p. 135-36°C	Cl: 18.75	18.88
				Quinoxaline derivative	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	Pale yellow micro needles, m.p. 171-72°C	Cl: 15.72
12.	Cl	Cl(2)	CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 122-23°C	Cl: 18.78	18.88

TABLE I (contd.)

No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	Formula	Properties	Analysis	
						Found	Reqd.
„				C ₂₄ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	Pale brown needles, m.p. 165-66°C	Cl: 15.78	15.85
13.	H	H	Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ClNO ₂ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 98-99°C	Cl: 10.74	10.84
„				C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 187-88°C	Cl: 8.81	8.89
14.	CH ₃	H	Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ClNO ₂ S	Yellow crystals, m.p. 103-104°C	Cl: 10.32	10.40
„				C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S	Yellow needles, m.p. 145-46°C	Cl: 8.48	8.59
15.	Cl	H	Cl	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 137-38°C	Cl: 19.48	19.61
„				C ₂₃ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 199-200°C	Cl: 16.28	16.36
16.	OCH ₃	H	Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ClNO ₃ S	Yellow soft needles, m.p. 106-107°C	Cl: 9.81	9.93
„				C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 163-64°C	Cl: 8.18	8.27
17.	Cl	Cl(3)	Cl	ClC ₁₇ H ₈ Cl ₃ NO ₂ S	Greenish yellow needles, m.p. 138-39°C	Cl: 26.8	26.86
„				C ₂₃ H ₁₂ Cl ₃ N ₃ S	Grayish white pdr., m.p. 205-206°C	Cl: 22.63	22.73
18.	Cl	Cl(2)	Cl	C ₁₇ H ₈ Cl ₃ NO ₂ S	Yellow crystals, m.p. 165-66°C	Cl: 26.76	26.86
„				C ₂₃ H ₁₂ Cl ₃ N ₃ S	Pale brown micro needles, m.p. 171-72°C	Cl: 22.61	22.73
19.	H	H	OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ NO ₃ S	Yellow needles, m.p. 99-100°C	N: 4.28	4.33
„				C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	Yellow needles, m.p. 151-52°C	N: 10.51	10.63
20.	CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO ₃ S	Yellow needles, m.p. 105-06°C	N: 4.01	4.15
„				C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	Pale yellow micro needles, m.p. 135-36°C	N: 10.22	10.27
21.	Cl	H	OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ClNO ₃ S	Yellow needles, m.p. 98-99°C	Cl: 9.84	9.93
„				C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 168-69°C	Cl: 8.16	8.27
22.	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO ₄ S	Yellow needles, m.p. 115-116°C	N: 3.90	3.97
„				C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 129-30°C	N: 9.79	9.88
23.	Cl	Cl(3)	OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NO ₃ S	Yellow micro needles, m.p. 133-34°C	Cl: 17.98	18.10
„				C ₂₄ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ OS	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 147-48°C	Cl: 15.21	15.30
24.	Cl	Cl(2)	OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ NO ₃ S	Yellow crystals, m.p. 170-71°C	Cl: 18.01	18.10
„				C ₂₄ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ OS	Gray micro needles, m.p. 153-54°C	Cl: 15.19	15.30

All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol.